

Neutrino Interaction Measurements with the SBND Experiment

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The Short-Baseline Neutrino Program

- Consists of three Liquid Argon Time Projection Chambers (LArTPCs) at different baselines along the Booster Neutrino Beam (BNB).
- Main program physics goal of searching for light ($\Delta m^2 \sim 1 \text{ eV}^2$) sterile neutrino oscillation.
- Three independent detector collaborations, each with its own standalone physics program.

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LArTPC Technology

LArTPCs are fully active tracking calorimeters - excellent at distinguishing complex final states.

- High 3D imaging resolution (\sim mm)
- Low energy thresholds (\sim MeV)
- Precise timing information using scintillation light (\sim ns)

Diagram Credit:
Maria Brigida Brunetti

Short Baseline Near Detector (SBND)

Main **SBND** goals include:

- Precision studies of ν -Ar interactions.
- Searches for physics beyond the Standard Model.
- 112 ton active volume LArTPC located 110 m from the BNB target.
- First started collecting data in July 2024.
- Completed its 1st period of neutrino beam data taking (December 2024 - July 2025), **currently collecting its 2nd dataset.**
- Collected ~3 million neutrino interactions - **largest dataset of ν -Ar interactions** to date!

Short Baseline Near Detector (SBND)

SBND is a 5 x 4 x 4 m³ detector consisting of 3 subsystems:

Time Projection Chamber:

- 2 TPCs (each with 2 m of drift distance) separated by a -100 kV central cathode.
- 3 wire planes in each anode ~11 k wires with 3 mm wire spacing [1].

Photon Detection System:

- Combines PMTs and X-ARAPUCA technology.
- Achieves excellent timing resolution O(ns) and high light yield [2].

Cosmic Ray Tagger:

- 7 external CRT walls made up of scintillation strips.
- Provides significant coverage to reject cosmic background.

Find out more about SBND and its current status in Bethany McCusker's talk today at 12:10!

[1] JINST 15 (2020) 06, P06033

[2] Eur. Phys. J. C 84 (2024) 10, 1046

ν -Ar Interactions in SBND

[1] The Short-Baseline Near Detector at Fermilab
arXiv:2504.00245 [hep-ex]

- BNB is a ν_μ beam ($\sim 94\%$) with a peak at ~ 0.8 GeV. Has $\bar{\nu}_\mu$ ($\sim 6\%$) and $\nu_e + \bar{\nu}_e$ ($\sim 0.5\%$) components.
- Due to its proximity to the beam target, SBND will collect an extremely high event rate of neutrino interactions (7000 neutrino events per day) \rightarrow inclusive and exclusive interaction measurements.

SBND Cross-Section Program

The large number of neutrino interactions in SBND allows for many in-depth physics studies:

CC = Charged-Current Interaction

NC = Neutral-Current Interaction

Rare Processes

ν -e elastic scattering

Induced nuclear clusters

$\nu_{\mu} \text{CC}\eta$

$\bar{\nu}_{\mu} \text{CC}\Lambda$

$\nu_{\mu} \text{CC}$ coherent π

$\nu_e \text{CC}$ from μDAR

$\nu_{\mu} \text{ CC } 1p0\pi^{\pm}$

$\sim 0.9\text{M } \nu_{\mu} \text{ CC } 1p0\pi^{\pm} \text{ events/year}$

- 1 proton ($p > 300 \text{ MeV}/c$), no other protons ($p > 200 \text{ MeV}/c$) and no charged pions. Current selection achieves 91% purity and 39% efficiency.
- Multi-dimensional measurement across:
 - Muon kinematics
 - Proton kinematics
 - Transverse kinematic imbalance variables
- Targets a quasi-elastic enhanced final-state and enables observation of low Q^2 effects.

ν_μ CC Inclusive

~2M ν_μ CC events/year

- Inclusive selection for first measurement.
- Highly pure sample (92%) at ~62% efficiency.
- Multi-dimensional measurement across muon kinematics.
- Early measurement that can demonstrate detector performance and understand flux effects.
- Low model dependency/ reduced FSI uncertainties.

ν_e CC Inclusive

- Uses shower features (opening angle, conversion gap and dE/dx) to identify electrons.
- For $E > 500$ MeV, selection purity of 81% with an efficiency of 30-40%.
- Important channel for the oscillation program (appearance).
- Utilises LArTPCs ability to distinguish electrons and photons - benchmark EM shower reconstruction and e/γ separation.

~15k ν_e CC events/year

NC π^0

~140k NC π^0 events/year

- π^0 with a 2γ decay. No π^\pm with $p > 150$ MeV/c.
- Two parallel final state selections:
 - With no protons
 - Protons ≥ 1
- Selection with no protons has purity of 53% with an efficiency of 22%.
- Measurement uses kinematics of the π^0 .
- Standard candle for calibration.
- Important background to ν_e analyses and BSM physics.

Other Analyses

ν_μ CC $1\pi^\pm$ Np

ν_μ CC Coherent π^\pm

η Resonant Production

- 1 π^\pm with no EM activity and any multiplicity of protons.
- Rich in resonant production.

- Low energy neutrino scattering off Ar nucleus with 1μ and $1\pi^\pm$ in final state.

- Search for resonances in the channel.
- Tuned selection to reject π^0 .

Summary

- SBND has been taking physics data for the past year - already collected the largest dataset of ν -Ar interactions to date with around 3 million interactions. Has been approved for 2 more years of data collection.
- SBND's LArTPC detector technology and proximity to the BNB target allows for a rich cross-section physics program.
- SBND's ν -Ar program will deliver:
 - High-statistics, multi-dimensional differential cross-section measurements.
 - World leading measurements of rare interaction channels.

Thank You!

SBND Collaboration Meeting - December 2025

Backup

X-ARAPUCA Technology

- Based on a photon trap concept.
- They confine the wavelength-shifted photons inside a highly reflective box where SiPMs capture them, effectively **increasing their collection area**.
- Collects and concentrates scintillation photons.

- One of the main goals for the X-ARAPUCA system in SBND is to search as R&D for this new technology and demonstrate its operation in a neutrino beam.

- 96 devices per TPC, half coated (pTB), half uncoated.
- Direct photons detected by coated, reflected photons detected by coated and uncoated.

BNB Flux

SBND-PRISM

[1] SBND-PRISM: Sampling Off-Axis Neutrino Fluxes with the Short-Baseline Near Detector
arXiv:2508.20239v1 [hep-ex]

- SBND is offset from the beam centre by 74 cm. At SBND's distance of 110 m from the target, this corresponds to an off-axis angular range of $[0^\circ, 1.6^\circ]$.
- Each neutrino interaction vertex position corresponds to a different off-axis angle within this range.
- Allows SBND to sample multiple off-axis fluxes using a single fixed detector - an additional handle for neutrino flux and interaction uncertainty constraints.

Electron/Photon Separation in LArTPCs

- LArTPCs are very good at electron/photon separation
- This is as a result of the fine-grained 3D imaging and calorimetric information they provide which allows for the following to be measured well:

1. Conversion gap:

- a. Electrons are charged so they start ionising the argon at the interaction vertex. **No gap** between the shower start and the interaction vertex
- b. Photons are neutral so they travel some distance before they become an e^+e^- pair. **Gap** between the shower start and interaction vertex

2. dE/dx at shower start:

- a. Electrons at the shower start have 1 MIP dE/dx
- b. Photons convert to an e^+e^- pair so that have 2 MIPs dE/dx at the shower start

[1] arXiv:2110.14065v3 [hep-ex]

Transverse Kinematic Imbalance (TKI) Variables

- TKI variables quantify imbalance in the transverse plane and are sensitive to nuclear effects such as:
 - Fermi motion
 - Multi-nucleon interactions
 - Final-state interactions (FSI)
- Transverse plane is defined as perpendicular to the neutrino beam direction.
- Using only transverse components reduces the dependence on neutrino energy.

TKI variables are powerful:

- Very small dependence on neutrino energy
- Directly probes nuclear effects

Common TKI variables:

- Transverse momentum imbalance, δp_T : Broadened by nuclear effects
- Transverse opening angle, $\delta\phi_T$: Peaks near 0° for balanced events
- Transverse acceleration angle, $\delta\alpha_T$: Peaks near 180° for balanced events

[1] Phys.Rev.C 94, 015503 (2016)

ν_{μ} CC Inclusive Selection

Cuts:

1. Flash match + not clear cosmic
2. Fiducial volume
3. Has at least one muon candidate (track like + $L > 32$ cm + is muon like)
4. Flash score
5. Low Z (muon candidate z-end point > 6 cm).

Largest background is non active volume neutrinos

ν_{μ} CC 1p0 π^{\pm} Selection

Cuts:

1. Not clear cosmic
2. Fiducial volume
3. CRUMBS score > 0 (cosmic rejection)
4. 1 candidate muon + 1 candidate proton
 - a. Muon: track > 50 cm, muon ID score < 30 , proton ID score > 100
 - b. Proton: not a muon candidate, proton ID score < 90
 - c. No stub like proton (based on stub length and dQ/dx)

Proton selection efficiency decreases with increasing momentum - harder to find Bragg peak because of rescatters

Backgrounds are ν_{μ} CC Np0 π , ν NC and ν_{μ} CC other

ν_e CC Inclusive Selection

Cuts:

1. Not clear cosmic
2. Fiducial volume
3. Flash matched but must be within beam spill window
4. Pandora slice has PFP with trackscore < 0.5 , shower energy > 200 MeV
5. Pandora neutrino score > 0.5
6. Particle tracks < 200 cm
7. Electron selection:
 - a. Conversion gap (distance between vertex and primary shower start) < 2 cm
 - b. dE/dx of primary shower between 1 and 2.5 MeV/cm
 - c. Opening angle of primary shower < 11.5 degrees

Backgrounds are ν_μ CC π^0 , ν NC π^0 ,

NC π^0 Selection

Cuts:

1. Not clear cosmic
2. Fiducial volume
3. CRUMBS score > -0.005
4. No razzled muons
5. Two razzled photons
6. Good π^0 kinematics
7. No razzled pions
8. No razzle protons

Biggest background is ν_μ CC with short muons